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Opportunities and challenges for harmonized
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1. Introduction

Comprehensive biodiversity databases are crucial for science, conservation, and sustainable resource use. Data on species occurrence that reliably record the name of the species and precise locations where it is found (herein, biodiversity databases) are central for the study of life on Earth. This information can be used as the basis for ecological studies, including research on species distributions and their changes, for example in relation to climate change (Rutgers et al., 2016). Data from biodiversity databases have also been used to assess progress towards targets on conserving biological diversity (European Commission Soil Monitoring Law?) and help identify management priorities that could allow the sustainable use of natural resources, for example, by maximizing productivity through maintaining high biodiversity in ecosystems like grasslands and arable lands to maximize productivity.

Currently, digital data is being produced at an accelerated rate, generating an information revolution that is affecting research around the globe. This big-data revolution is also manifested by a wealth of online biodiversity databases. Many biodiversity databases are now available through the internet, and their data are being gathered at a rapid rate with the aid of internet-based data sharing portals and biodiversity information networks. There are scores of international and national efforts to collate biodiversity data. There is, however, no guide that could help navigate the diversity of sources available or let the general user choose the most suitable database to fulfil a specific objective (Guerra et al., 2021). To answer a scientific question, many researchers use only one database, without considering the alternatives or how they compare. It has been long acknowledged, however, that scientists should navigate multiple databases to obtain all information available on a particular species (Guerra et al., 2021)

Major biodiversity data aggregators, like GBIF, began providing georeferenced species records in 2004 and have since amassed a vast dataset of 1.4 billion records, approximately 150,000 of those concerning earthworms. Edaphobase (Burkhardt et al., 2014) is the largest soil fauna database of Europe and contains plot-level data on abundances or biomasses, which is essential to best examine earthworm distributions quantitatively. Though Edaphobase is largely restricted to Germany, natural ecosystems and macrofauna. In addition, both these databases lack metadata associated with the earthworm data, which still remains a knowledge gap (Phillips et al., 2021). Thus, there is a clear need to analyze the main earthworm data in agroecosystems and especially their reusability based on their metadata availability.

In the face of rapid global changes, a grand challenge is efficiently cataloguing, assessing, and responding to changes in soil biodiversity and associated ecosystem functions. Addressing this challenge requires unprecedented access to biodiversity data across spatial, temporal, and taxonomic scales. However, heterogeneous coverage, protocols, and standards have hampered integration among these databases. To stimulate the next stage of data integration, here we present a report a synthesis of two major earthworm databases and investigate (a) how the coverage of databases varies across taxonomy, space, and record type; (b) what degree of integration is present among databases; (c) how integration of databases can increase biodiversity knowledge; and (d) the barriers to database integration.

The specific goals are to quantify

Proposed Activities:

- Synthesize and describe the databases in terms of database size, quantity of earthworm data, species richness (if possible) and abundances.
- Quantify the amount of overlap between different databases. Describe the geographic distributions of species records and species richness.

- I.e., Compare available biodiversity databases, and understanding their weaknesses, strengths and potential is needed if we are to make informed use of biodiversity data and derive appropriate research conclusions and management advice.

2. Methodological approach

Selected established biodiversity databases (Edaphobase, sWorm from iDiv) that mainly focus on geographic distributions will be reviewed. The integration status and major knowledge gaps and barriers to full integration between databases will be assessed. Finally, how improved integration can increase the data coverage for selected soil biodiversity indicators (e.g., earthworms) in different databases will be estimated.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Attributes of databases

Edaphobase is a database collating data on all soil biota (Burkhardt et al. 2014). At the time of publication, it contains 28,905 observations¹ of earthworms in total, but only 15,725 observations in agricultural areas as per Corine Land Cover. The vast majority of the observations are from Germany, with only very few additional ones originating from Serbia, Austria and Bulgaria. To access the data, a free account must be created, but then this gives access to a multitude of filters and even data visualization tools. A full dataset downloaded from Edaphobase contains 321 columns in total, relating to data origin, sampling methodology, habitat, soil, and climate, though information is not always available for all these variables (Figure 1). For example, the geographical location of the sampling sites (latitude, longitude) is unknown for 6,703 observations out of the 15,725, which limits further usability of the data, as geographical location can be used for further data extrapolation. Additionally, among the multitude of variables are many that serve as qualitative remarks about the data. These remarks sometimes contain important information, e.g. about agricultural management, but cannot be easily processed automatically due to their heterogeneity and information being spread over several columns. As for availability of earthworm data, the dataset contains 79 different entries for taxa. Given that the vast majority of the data comes from Germany, and Germany is home to only 46 known earthworm species (Lehmitz et al. 2014), this means that this number is inflated due to additional entries on sub-species, genus or even family-level, and also some of the species found in the other countries that are part of the dataset. Considering all of this, 67 different species-level entries could be found in this dataset.

The sWorm database (Phillips et al. 2021) is openly available on the iDiv data repository (<https://idata.idiv.de/>). It contains specifically earthworm data on a global scale in several different habitats (24,604 observations). Limiting the dataset to agricultural land in Europe, this number is reduced to 5,815 observations. While this dataset contains data for 25 countries in Europe, there are often only very few datapoints per country. The available metadata is limited in comparison to Edaphobase with only 57 columns in this dataset, relating also to data origin, sampling methodology, habitat, and soil. This dataset does not contain any climate variables. Information on agricultural metadata is much more easily processed automatically, however, as the data is very structured and homogenous. The geographical location of sampling sites is also available for all data points, allowing easier extrapolation of additional data. This dataset contains 53 different entries for taxa, but this number is not inflated by genus-level entries, which means that it really contains data on 53 different

¹ One observation is equal to the observation of one taxon (be it species, genus, or family level) at one sampling site. Therefore, one sampling site has as many observations associated with it as there were different taxa found in it.

information on sampling method of earthworms in 12.5% of data points. This is an issue, as sampling method is an important factor influencing the abundance of earthworms found (Coja et al. 2008). Interestingly, while Edaphobase covers a much smaller geographic region, it includes more different taxa compared to sWorm.

4. Conclusions

Impact:

Rapid increases in biodiversity knowledge can be achieved through the integration of databases, providing the data necessary to address critical environmental challenges. Harmonized databases would be helpful to clarify the relationships among biodiversity databases, in particular what is the unique data coverage of each database and what are the dataflows among biodiversity databases. The future databases must focus on the essential goal to maximize compatibility, minimize barriers to dataflow. This will increase reproducibility and reusability of available data and thus narrow major knowledge gaps between existing global soil biodiversity databases.

Lack of metadata makes data basically unusable. The problem of irreproducibility is compounded by the rise of big data, where large volumes of unformatted sources of data have been made accessible. However, lack of harmonized data, dataset metadata and standardized vocabularies were considered a primary stumbling block to reproducible research and decision-making using big data in national and international monitoring initiatives (eg. soil carbon farming, biodiversity monitoring, soil health etc.,). The data collected in this work provides an example of harmonized data that facilitates decision making, management assessments and modelling, which was carried out in Minotaur WP5 to map the distribution of selected biological indicators. (in D5.1 and D5.2).

Thus, it is essential to enhance the involvement of stakeholders in improving quality of data archiving and decision making.

5. References

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